

Antimicrobial Finish in Textiles

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Abstract:

The consumers are now increasingly aware of the hygienic life style and there is a necessity and expectation for a wide range of textile products finished with antimicrobial properties. In the development of fabrics, functional aspects such as anti-bacterial and UV protection are playing an increased important role. To protect the mankind and to avoid cross contamination, a special finish like antimicrobial finish has become necessary. As consumers have become more aware of hygiene and potentially harmful effects of microbes, the demand for antimicrobial finished clothing is increasing. The population explosion and the environmental pollution in recent years have forced researchers to find new health and hygiene related products for the wellbeing of mankind. The threats caused by microbes are numerous and the problem is aggravated even more in tropical and subtropical regions. Pathogenic microorganisms transfer infectious diseases and cause lung related disorders. Mould and fungi cause staining, discoloration and degradation of textile substrates, particularly those made of natural fibres (protein and cellulosic fibres). Nowadays, there is a good deal of demand for fabrics with antimicrobial finishes to protect human beings against microbes. The application of antimicrobial textile finishes includes a wide range of textile products for medical, technical, industrial, home furnishing and apparel sectors.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, Antibacterial, functional, Hygienic, Microbes

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1. Introduction

Hygiene has become essential to human beings way of life. Consumers' attitude towards hygiene and active lifestyle has created a rapidly increasing market for a wide range of functional textiles, which in turn has stimulated intensive research and development. Value addition in clothing has changed the global textile scenario. Research has quite convincingly shown that apparel consumers all over the world are demanding functionality in the products that they use. When textile assumes an additional function over and above the conventional purpose, it may be regarded as speciality or functional textile. To realize our dream of new fibres and environment friendly wet processing, it is essential to invest in future research and "researchers" [1, 2].

The textile industry of the future looks very promising – something to revive our spirits considering the fact that it is considered an obsolete technology. However, the textile industry is required to shift its emphasis from "quantity" to "quality" and adopt itself to the dynamism of the market economy. As a result, the number of bio functional textiles with an antimicrobial activity has increased considerably over the last few years. Some of the best examples of functionality are the products attributes such as wrinkle resistance, soil release, flame retardant, oil repellency, fade resistance, UV resistance, anti-allergy, insect repellent, stain release, anti odour, microbial resistance, fragrance release, protective finishes, skin care additives, insect repellent, deodorizing fragrance, antimicrobials, cool finish and thermal insulator finish, water proofing finish and UV stabilizers. Functional finishes represent the next generation of finishing industry, which make textile materials act by themselves. This means that they may keep us warm in cold environments or cool in hot environments or provide us with considerable convenience, support, and even fun in our normal day-to-day activities [3].

2. Antimicrobial finish

2.1 Need for Antimicrobial Finish in Textiles

The term 'antimicrobial' refers to a broad range of technologies that provide varying degrees of protection for textile materials against microorganisms. Antimicrobials are very different in their chemical nature, mode of action, impact on people and the environment, handling characteristics, durability, costs, regulatory compliance, and how they interact with microorganisms. The purpose of imparting antimicrobial activity to textiles is to protect the material from microbial attack, prevent the transmission and spreading of pathogenic microorganisms, inhibit odour development resulting from microbial degradation, and creating a material that will act as preventive and/or curative treatment. Ideal antimicrobial finishing needs to fulfill a number of requirements in order to achieve the maximum benefit from antimicrobially functionalized textile products. An antimicrobially-treated material is defined as being hygienic and, therefore, should have the following requirements. Effective inhibition against a broad spectrum of bacterial and fungal species, non-toxicity to the consumer, manufacturer and the environment, durability, compatibility with resident skin micro biota, and other finishing processes, avert from irritations and allergies, applicability with no adverse effects on the quality or appearance of the textile [4].

In recent years, great interest in the antibacterial finishing of fibres and fabrics for practical applications has been observed. Most textile materials currently used in hospitals and hotels are conducive to cross-infection or transmission of diseases caused by micro-organisms. Textiles for medical and hygienic use have become important areas in the textile industry. In general, antimicrobial properties can be imparted to textile materials by chemically or physically incorporating functional agents onto fibres or fabrics. The antimicrobial properties of such textile materials can be grouped into two categories, temporarily or durably functional fabrics [5].

Temporary biocidal properties of fabrics are easy to achieve in finishing, but easy to lose in laundering. Durability has generally been accomplished by a common technology, a slow-releasing method. According to this method, sufficient antibacterial agents are incorporated into fibres or fabrics by means of a wet finishing process. The treated fabrics deactivate bacteria by slowly releasing the biocide from the materials. However, the antibacterial agents will vanish completely if they are impregnated in materials without covalent bond linkages. The inherent properties of the textile fibres provide room for the growth of microorganisms. Besides, the structure of the substrates and the chemical processes may induce the growth of microbes. Humid and warm environment still aggravate the problem. Infestation by microbes causes cross infection by pathogens and develop odour where the fabric is worn next to skin. In addition, the staining and loss of the performance properties of textile substrates are the results of microbial attack. Basically, with a view to protecting the wearer and the textile substrate itself antimicrobial finish is applied to textile materials [6].

Antimicrobial are used on textiles to control bacteria, fungi, mold, mildew, and algae and the problems of deterioration, staining, odour and health concerns that they cause. In the broad array of microorganisms there are both good and bad types. Control strategies of the bad organisms must include consideration of being sure that non-target organisms are not affected or that adaptation of microorganisms is not encouraged.

Microorganisms cause problems with textile raw materials and processing chemicals, wet processes in the mills, roll or bulk goods in storage, finished goods in storage and transport, and goods as they are used by the consumer. This can be extremely critical to a clean room operator, a medical facility, or a food processing facility, or it can be an annoyance and aesthetic problem to the athlete or normal consumers. The economic impact of microbial contamination is significant and the consumer interests and demands for protection is at an all-time high.

Antibacterial fabrics are important not only in medical applications but also in terms of daily life usage. The application of antimicrobial finishes to textiles can prevent bacterial growth on textiles. Antibacterial textile production has become increasingly prominent for hygienic and medical applications. The antimicrobial agents can be antibiotics, formaldehyde, heavy metal ions (silver, copper), quaternary ammonium salts with long hydrocarbon chains, phenol and oxidizing agents such as chlorine, chloramines, hydrogen peroxide, ozone. Antimicrobial Finish is important for general textiles and high performance applications where the chance of microbial growth is high [7].

Antimicrobials fabrics gained significant importance due to their wide acceptance as surgical apparels, baby clothing and undergarments. In the last few decades, with the increase in new antimicrobial fibre technologies and the growing awareness about cleaner surroundings and healthy lifestyle, a range of textile products based on synthetic antimicrobial agents such as triclosan, metal and their salts, organometallics, phenols and quaternary

ammonium compounds, have been developed and quite a few are also available commercially. Although the synthetic antimicrobial agents are very effective against a range of microbes and give a durable effect on textiles, they are a cause of concern due to the associated side effects, action on non-target microorganisms and water pollution. Hence, there is a great demand for antimicrobial textiles based on ecofriendly agents which not only help to reduce effectively the ill effects associated due to microbial growth on textile material but also comply with the statutory requirements imposed by regulating agencies [8].

Cellulose fibres have found a broad application in medical textile field owing to the unique characteristic, such as high moisture and liquid adsorption, low impurity content, antistatic behavior, and good mechanical properties. However, cellulose fibres provide an excellent surface for microorganisms' growth. Due to their molecular structure and a large active surface area, cellulose fibres, may be an ideal matrix for the design of bioactive, biocompatible, and intelligent materials. According to the literature cellulose fibres are one of the most interesting basic materials for antimicrobial fictionalization. The surface modification of the cellulose fibres is currently considered to be the best route for obtaining modern functionality on textiles for the use in medical applications. However, in spite of various techniques used for fibre fictionalization in order to impart antimicrobial properties and to develop biomedical products, there is still a large gap within the research field of interactions between bacterial and fungal systems and bioactive surfaces of medical textile materials. Standard test methods are commonly applied to determine the efficiency of antimicrobial agents. These methods do not usually reflect in-use circumstances, because the majority of tests have only been performed in liquid media and not on dry, complex heterogeneous systems such as functionalized fibrous materials. Testing and evaluating antimicrobial efficiency in laboratory conditions with respect to the real-life environment is rather challenging. Thus, the test selected and interpretations made may vary on the basis of the different capability of antimicrobial action. The evaluation of any antimicrobial test results requires a thoughtful and basic understanding of microbiology, understanding the strengths and limitations of each test and understanding the mode of action of the antimicrobial agent in question [9].

Following are the major requirement for an effective antimicrobial finish:

1. Durability to washing, dry cleaning and hot pressing
2. Selective activity to undesirable microbes
3. It should not produce harmful effects to the manufacture, user and the environment
4. It should compile with the statutory requirements of regulating agencies
5. Compatibility with the chemical processes
6. Easy method of application
7. No deterioration of fabric quality
8. Resistant to the body fluids
9. Resistant to disinfectant/sterilization
10. Quick acting and effective in killing or inhibiting the growth of a broad spectrum of microbes
11. Non-selective and non-mutable to pathogens
12. Fast to repeated laundering, dry cleaning and exposure to light
13. Safe and comfortable to wear (No irritation to skin)
14. Minimal environmental impact
15. Compatible with other finishing agents
16. Low cost

Antimicrobial treatment for textile materials in necessary to fulfill the following objectives:

1. To avoid cross infection by pathogenic microorganisms.
2. To control the infestation by microbes
3. To arrest metabolism in microbes in order to reduce the formation of odour.
4. To safeguard the textile products from staining, discoloration and quality deterioration

2.2 Need for Herbal Antimicrobial Finish

There is significant development in investigation of eco-friendly, natural antimicrobial finish for application on textile substrate.

The following requirements need to be satisfied to obtain maximum benefits out of the finish:

1. Durability to washing, dry-cleaning and hot pressing.
2. Selective activity to undesirable microorganisms.

3. Should not produce harmful effects to the manufacturer, user and the environment.
4. Should comply with the statutory requirements of regulating agencies.
5. Compatibility with the chemical processes.
6. Easy method of application. No deterioration of fabric quality.
7. Resistant to body fluids; and resistant to disinfections / sterilization

The natural variants possess more potential for investigation because of following reasons:

1. Eco-friendly
2. Least toxicity
3. Suitability for next-to-skin innerwear
4. Vast scope of research to counteract microbe's resistant development towards antimicrobial finishes
5. Safe handling.

Nature has been a source of medicinal agents and has been isolated from natural sources. Many of these isolations were based on the uses of the agents in traditional medicine. The plant-based, traditional medicine systems continue to play an essential role in health care [10]. Among these, development of antimicrobial textile finish is highly indispensable and relevant since garments are in direct contact with human body. Though a number of commercial antimicrobial agents have been introduced in the market, their compliance to the regulations imposed by international bodies like EPU is still unclear. The herbal antimicrobial finishes overcome the disadvantages of chemical finishes. They will not cause damage to the fabrics, are eco-friendly, non-toxic, non-allergic and since naturally occurring herbs are used, the cost factor is also feasible [11]. Extracts of medicinal herbs-in particular essential oils-have shown many potential applications in folk medicine, fragrance, cosmetic, phyto-preparations and food technology as reported by several researchers [12]. Several medicinal and herbal plants are indigenous to the Mediterranean region [13-16] the unique geographical locations of Jordan led to the diversity in its ecological and climate regions. Aromatic plants have been used in folk medicine as antimicrobial agents since ancient times.

3. Microorganisms involved in textiles

Mould, mildew, fungus, yeast, bacteria and virus (micro-organisms) are part of our everyday lives. There are both good and bad types of microorganisms. The thousands of species of micro-organisms that exist are found everywhere in the environment, on our garments and on our bodies. Microbes, their body parts, metabolic products and reproductive parts, cause multiple problems to textiles. These are human irritants, sensitizers, toxic-response agents, causers of disease and simple discomforting agents.

3.1 The Microbial Growth Promoters

The human skin is usually crowded with innumerable microbes. In favourable conditions certain bacteria can grow from a single germ to million in a very short period of time. They can double every 20 to 30 minutes in a warm and moist micro climate that has plenty of food for them, e.g. perspiration and other body secretion, skin particles, fats and leftovers from worn out threads. The common promoters are as following:

1. Temperature
2. Moisture
3. Dirt
4. Receptive Surface
5. Perspiration
6. Food Particles
7. Textile Finishes

Although microbes can be useful in many ways e.g. in brewing, baking and biotechnology, they can also be harmful to both textile and humans. The various effects of microbes are stated as follows:

1. Bad Odour
2. Skin and Soft Tissue Infections
3. Staining of Fabric
4. Slick slimy handle
5. Loss of Functional Properties
6. Decrease in Life of textile

Cotton textiles in contact with the human body offer an ideal environment for microbial growth. Microbes are the tiniest creature not seen by naked eyes. They include a variety of microorganisms like bacteria, fungi, algae and

virus. Bacteria are unicellular organisms which grow rapidly under ideal condition like moisture and warmth. Subdivision of the bacteria family includes two classes Gram positive and Gram negative, of which *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* respectively are the typical examples. Some specific types of bacteria are pathogenic and cause cross infection. Fungi, moulds or mildew are complex organisms with slow growth rate. They stain the fabric and deteriorate its performance properties. To protect the textiles and mankind from pathogen and to avoid cross infection, a special finish like antimicrobial finish has become necessary [17].

The mechanism is either on the cell during the metabolism or within the core substance (genome). Oxidizing agents such as aldehydes, halogens and peroxy compounds attack the cell membrane, get into cytoplasm and affect the enzymes of the micro-organism. Coagulants, primary alcohols irreversibly denature the protein structure. Radical formers like halogens, isothiazones and peroxy compounds are highly reactive due to the presence of free electrons. These compounds virtually react with all organic structure in particular risk to nucleic acids by triggering mutations and dimerization. There are many natural/herbal products which show antimicrobial activities [18].

Microbial shedding from our body contributes to microorganism spreading into a textile material either directly in clothes or on surrounding textiles. Recent studies strongly support that contamination of textiles in clinical settings may contribute to the dispersal of pathogens to the air which then settle down and infect the immediate and non-immediate environment. It is one of the most probable causes of hospital infections [19].

Typically, pathogenic microorganisms like *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* have been found on textiles. In addition, microorganism proliferation can cause malodours, stains and damage the mechanical properties of the component fibres that could cause a product to be less effective in its intended use. Additionally, may promote skin contamination, inflammation and in sensitive people, atopic dermatitis [20].

4. Functional Finishes on Textiles

Functionalization of textile materials can be defined as a process which provides functional properties to textile and clothing materials. Functional properties can be obtained either by:

- The fibre itself (characteristics of the polymer or additives before fibre spinning)
- Yarn, fabric or material construction (for instance, with different fibres or different layers)
- Textile finishing

This can be made by all the traditional technologies, such as: exhaustion, padding, low add-on processes, foam application, printing, coating, etc. The innovative effects are assured by the application of specialty chemicals which can be applied by means of new alternative supports, such as microencapsulation, by using cyclodextrines. These alternatives are now very important for the application of several functional finishes, especially when a long term effect is intended, with controlled release of chemicals. The emergence of the so-called “nanotechnologies” opens also a wide range of new possibilities. In many cases, the functional properties involve a surface modification, which can be obtained by means of chemical modification, by the application of a surface layer or by more environmental friendly treatments such as the use of enzymes or physical modification (based namely on plasma technology).

The consumers are demanding textile products with higher performances, even in the “traditional” clothing and home textiles areas. In fact, significant product differentiation in the area of textiles can be achieved by high performance properties, in parallel with visual appearance. Some of these properties were developed mainly for “protective” clothing but nowadays they are often present in functional textiles used for “normal” clothing. Many fabric producers are devoting more and more attention to try to put into the market products with new effects that can represent an important added value.

The many antimicrobial agents used in textile applications include halogenated salicylic acid, anilides, aromatic halogen compounds, chlorinated diphenylethers (Triclosan), benzoic esters, metal compounds (e.g., Ag, Zn, Cu), quaternary ammonium compounds, and chitosan. Antimicrobial agents can be integrated into the fibres directly or can be applied to textile surfaces by conventional textile finishing processes. The main advantages of finishing are higher productivity and relatively low processing cost. However, many textiles finished this way have lower durability against repeated home launderings than the fabrics consisting of antibacterial fibres.

4.1 Antimicrobial Finishing Methodologies

The antimicrobial agents can be applied to the textile substrates by exhaust, pad-dry-cure, coating, spray and foam techniques. The substances can also be applied by directly adding into the fibre spinning dope. It is claimed that the commercial agents can be applied online during the dyeing and finishing operations. Various methods for improving the durability of the finish include:

1. Insolubilisation of the active substances in / on the fibre.
2. Treating the fibre with resin, condensates or cross-linking agents.
3. Micro encapsulation of the antimicrobial agents with the fibre matrix.
4. Coating the fibre surface.
5. Chemical modification of the fibre by covalent bond formation.
6. Use of graft polymers, homo polymers and / or co-polymerization on to the fibre.

4.1.1 Types of Antimicrobial Agent

There are several different classifications for antimicrobial agents in the literature according to the chemistry, the mechanism of antimicrobial activity, efficiency, and washing-resistance. Consistent with these studies, antimicrobial substances can be divided into biocides and biostats, leaching and bound antimicrobials, controlled-release and barrier-forming agents, synthetic and natural, and agents of poor and of good washing resistance. In general, the antimicrobial agents can have a biocidal or biostatic effect on microbial growth rates. Whilst the biocides (bactericides and fungicides) cause the death of microorganisms, the biostats (bacteriostats and fungistats) lead to the inhibition of the microorganisms' growth. The mode of action is strongly dependent upon the concentration of the active substance in the textile. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is required for biostatic activity, while the minimum biocidal concentration (MBC) should be exceeded for biocidal activity. Many commercially-used antimicrobial products, e.g. silver, triclosan, polyhexamethylen biguanid (PHMB) and quaternary ammonium compounds are biocides.

4.1.2 Mechanism of Antimicrobials

Development of antimicrobials for clinical use has been most successful in targeting essential components of 5 general areas of bacterial metabolism: cell wall synthesis, protein synthesis, RNA synthesis, DNA synthesis, and intermediary metabolism. It is beyond the scope of this discussion to cover each of these areas in detail. Instead, focus on some recent developments in novel inhibitors that target dual steps in cell wall synthesis, in understanding the pathways by which antimicrobial agents of diverse types may effect cell killing, and in understanding the interactions of quinolones with their dual targets and the consequences of these interactions.

Mechanisms of action of antibacterial agents are given below

- Interference with cell wall synthesis

β -Lactams: penicillin, cephalosporin, carbapenems, Monobactams

Glycopeptides: vancomycin, teicoplanin

- Protein synthesis inhibition

Bind to 50S ribosomal subunit: macrolides, chloramphenicol, clindamycin, quinupristin-dalfopristin, linezolid.

Bind to 30S ribosomal subunit: aminoglycosides, tetracyclines

Bind to bacterial isoleucyl-tRNA synthetase: mupirocin reference with nucleic acid synthesis

Inhibit DNA synthesis: fluoroquinolones

Inhibit RNA synthesis: rifampin

- Inhibition of metabolic pathway: sulfonamides, folic acid analogues
- Disruption of bacterial membrane structure: polymyxins, daptomycin.

On the basis of the number of antimicrobials in clinical use, bacterial cell wall synthesis has been perhaps the target area most extensively exploited for antimicrobial development, although bacterial protein synthesis may be a close second. The components of the cell wall synthesis machinery are appealing antimicrobial targets because of the absence of counterparts in human biology, thereby providing intrinsic target selectivity. It is possible to determine the site in the synthesis pathway at which an antimicrobial acts by measuring accumulation of precursors and blocks in development of immature and mature peptidoglycan. β -Lactam antimicrobials are known to interact with transpeptidase directly, forming covalent linkages that have enabled the study of their actions by use of labeled β -lactam molecules to tag these enzymes, which are also designated penicillin binding proteins because of this property.

Bactericidal activity is a general property of β -lactams, glycopeptides, amino glycosides, and quinolones. For all of these classes, however, interaction with their various drug targets, cell wall synthesis for β -lactams and glycopeptides, the bacterial ribosome for amino glycosides, and DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV for quinolones, although a necessary initial event, is not by itself sufficient to affect bacterial lethality. Subsequent events are required, but the molecular nature of these events has been elusive. β -Lactams as transpeptidase inhibitors thus block the conversion of immature to mature peptidoglycan. Because many bacteria have several distinct but essential transpeptidase, β -lactam resistance by target alteration requires alteration of several targets, making development of high-level resistance by mutation.

4.1.3 Commercial Antimicrobial Agents and Fibres

Thomson Research Associates markets a range of antimicrobials under the trade name Ultra fresh for the textile and polymer industry. Ultra fresh products were developed to be used in normal textile processes. To incorporate antibacterial into high temperature fibres like polyester and nylon, it is necessary to use an inorganic antimicrobial like Ultra fresh CA-16 or PA-42. These must be added as a special master batch to the polymer mixture before the extrusion process. For fibres such as polypropylene, which are extruded at lower temperatures, it is possible to use organic antimicrobials such as Ultra fresh Nm-100, Dm-50 or XQ-32. In the case of Rossari.s Fabshield with AEGIS microbe shield programme, the cell membrane of the bacteria get ruptured when the microbes come in contact with the treated surface; thus, preventing consumption of antimicrobial over a period of time and remain functional throughout the life of the product. The active substance 3-Trimethoxy silyl propyl dimethyl octadecyl ammonium chloride gets attached to the substrate either through bond formation on the surface or by micro polymer-sing and forming a layer on the treated surface; the antimicrobial agent disrupts the cell membrane of the microbes through physical and ionic phenomena. Ciba Specialty Chemicals markets Tinosan AM 110 as a durable antimicrobial agent for textiles made of polyester and polyamide fibres and their blends with cotton, wool or other fibres.

Tinosan contains an active antimicrobial (2, 4, 4'-Trichloro-2' - hydroxyl-dipenylether) which behaves like a colorless disperse dye and can be exhausted at a very high exhaustion rate on to polyester and polyamide fibres when added to the dye bath. Clariant markets the Sanitized range of Sanitized AG, Switzerland for the hygienic finish of both natural and synthetic fibres. The branded Sanitized range functions as a highly effective bacteriostatic and fungistatic finishes and can be applied to textile materials such as ladies hosiery and tights.

4.1.4 Benefits of Antimicrobial Textiles

A wide range textile product is now available for the benefit of the consumer. Initially, the primary objective of the finish was to protect textiles from being affected by microbes particularly fungi. Uniforms, tents, defense textiles and technical textiles, such as, geo-textiles have therefore all been finished using antimicrobial agents. Later, the home textiles, such as, curtains coverings, and bath mats came with antimicrobial finish. The application of the finish is now extended to textiles used for outdoor, healthcare sector, sports and leisure. Novel technologies in antimicrobial finishing are successfully employed in nonwoven sector especially in medical textiles. Textile fibres with built-in antimicrobial properties will also serve the purpose alone or in blends with other fibres. Bioactive fibre is a modified form of the finish, which includes chemotherapeutics in their structure, i.e., synthetic drugs of bactericidal and fungicidal qualities. These fibres are not only used in medicine and health prophylaxis applications but also for manufacturing textile products of daily use and technical textiles. The field of application of the bioactive fibres includes sanitary materials, dressing materials, surgical threads, materials for filtration of gases and liquids, air conditioning and ventilation, constructional materials, special materials for food industry, pharmaceutical industry, footwear industry, clothing industry, automotive industry, etc.

4.1.5 Evaluation of Antimicrobial Efficiency

Testing the antimicrobial activity of functionalized textiles is consisted of two categories of standardized test methods, qualitative (AATCC TM147 and AATCC TM30 (antifungal) (American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists Test Method), ISO/DIS 20645, EN ISO 20645 and ISO 11721 (International Standards Organization), and SN 195 920 (921 - antifungal) (Swiss Norm) and quantitative (AATCC TM100, ISO 20743, SN 195924, JIS L 1902 (Japanese Industrial Standard) and ASTM E 2149 (American Society for Testing and Materials). Qualitative methods are mostly based on the agar diffusion test. They are relatively quick, cheap, simple and well-defined but subjective (use of ratings) and not appropriate for all kind of textiles and for analyses of efficacy of different antimicrobial agents as they diffuse through agar at different rates or not at all. Quantitative Bacterial Reduction Test (AATCC test method 100-2004).

Quantitative methods are on the other hand more broadly applicable but more time-intensive and expensive as they involve actual microbe enumeration, indicating level of bactericidal/ fungicidal activity. They can be used for all types of textiles and antimicrobials and comparisons can be made between different antimicrobial treatments as well as various treatment levels on the same textile. The more commonly used tests for evaluation of the antimicrobial efficiency are Parallel Streak Method AATCC TM147 and ISO 20645, from among qualitative tests and AATCC TM100, JIS L 1902 and ISO 20743, from among quantitative tests.

4.1.6 Advantages of antimicrobial finished cotton fabric

The specific antimicrobial activity or bacterio static effects is based on the difference between the bacteria count of the reference value (Mb value) and the sample after 18 h of incubation (Mc value). Due to the limitations of the existing system, a new test system EN ISO20645, SN 195920-1992 /TC/38/WG23 (test methods for antimicrobial finished textile products) has been evolved by considering the technological, dermatological and ecological aspects of the finish.

5. Conclusion

An antimicrobial finish can be applied to most types of textiles. A wide variety of antimicrobial finishes are currently being applied to nonwoven textiles to be used as disposable protective garments in hospitals. Antimicrobials textiles, whether woven, nonwoven, or knit, can also be made out of any type of fibre content that is suitable for garment production. The fibre content of an antimicrobial textile must be chosen carefully. Synthetic fabrics may not be appropriate for some end uses due to the fact that most synthetic fibres are hydrophobic. This means that fabrics made of synthetic fibres hold a large amount of perspiration wetness in their weave structure than do natural fibres. This property can cause an increased chance of irritation and odor due to microbial growth on the body. Antimicrobial textiles with improved functionality find a variety of applications such as health and hygiene products, specially the garments worn close to the skin and several medical applications, such as infection control and barrier material.

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